

Education Quarterly Reviews

**Karatepe, Ramazan, İnandı, Yusuf, and Akar Karatepe, Duygu. (2021),
Academicians' Views on Career Barriers and Academic Alienation. In:
Education Quarterly Reviews, Vol.4, No.2, 152-165.**

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.04.02.207

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Academics' Views on Career Barriers and Academic Alienation

Ramazan Karatepe¹, Yusuf İnandır², Duygu Akar Karatepe³

¹ Department of Curriculum Development and Instruction, Faculty of Education, University of Mersin, Turkey

² Department of Education Management, Faculty of Education, University of Mersin, Turkey

³ Turkey Ministry of Education

Correspondence: Ramazan Karatepe: Mersin University Faculty of Education Çiftlikköy Campus, 33343, Yenişehir / Mersin/Turkey. E-mail: rkaratepe@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of this study is to reveal the relationship between academics' career barriers and academic alienation. General screening model which is used in the research work of the working group in Turkey are 203 state universities academics. In the study, 19-item Career Barrier Scale was used to determine the career barriers of academics, and the Academic Alienation Scale with 21 items was used to determine the level of academic alienation. According to the results of the research, there is a positive relationship between career barriers and isolation. In addition, isolation is explained by career barriers to a great extent.

Keywords: Academician, Career Barriers, Academic Alienation

1. Introduction

An important part of the working life cycle is shaped by career. Individuals make their choices by taking career stages into consideration while choosing a profession and changing a profession. Because the career development process of that profession is significantly effective in most of the material and moral concerns in professional life. These concerns differ periodically in the choice of profession. In the past, since the development stages of business life were not shaped as much as today, sustainability was provided with one profession, one job, one wage. However, the present systematic processes such as changing the form of business mentality, staging the professional life of the individual, and planning differentiate the duties and responsibilities of the employees in the organization. These diversity and transitions add significant intensity to the career process of the employee within the organization and create various obstacles for a healthy and productive work life. This situation, which is explained as career barriers, can create negative situations for the employees by creating new orders in organizations.

When the reasons for career barriers are examined, it is seen that two titles, individual and organizational, stand out. The most important organizational obstacles are being fired, being prevented, being disgraced, stress and burnout, glass ceiling syndrome, organizational culture and policies, and not being able to join the communication network (Alaçam, 2014). Although these reasons are considered as a part of the development of the organization, they are seen as a career obstacle on an individual basis. Individual career barriers, on the other hand, are related to the right of the individual to lead a satisfying professional life in terms of social, psychological and economic aspects as a requirement of being human (İnandı, Tunç, & Uslu, 2013). Individuals are faced with a great career obstacle when they do not continue their journey by discovering their own capacity, realizing their deficiencies and improving them, increasing their motivation in economic and social terms. These obstacles lead to the development of many different negative situations and attitudes in employees.

Career barriers are observed more prominently, especially in multi-population organizations. Since the high number of employees significantly affects the amount and quality of production, competition among employees increases, causing career phases to come to the fore frequently in that organization. Universities are one of the organizations with this agenda. The large number of lecturers, scientific encouragement, motivation, quality publication, increasing previous knowledge and experience cause the individuals to enter a competition both in their own cycle and with their colleagues. These expressions, which are the keywords of career development, add a progressive perspective to the career process in universities, and can also be an obstacle to prevent this progress. In particular, career development processes of faculty members in their professional lives constitute one of the main goals of the profession. Therefore, the career barriers they encounter not only stop a progress, but also create a multi-faceted picture of negativity. Lack of belonging to the organization, decrease in organizational trust, increase in destructive conflicts, and alienation are among the topics frequently encountered in this picture. Especially the predictive power of alienation is of great importance in the foundation of this study. Considering the recent studies on academic, it is seen that career barriers have been addressed to a great extent. However, research on academic alienation is very limited. There are no studies that deal with career barriers and academic alienation together. Therefore, this study examines the career barriers and academic alienation of academicians in order to fill the gap at this point and to shed light on future studies. In addition, addressing the causes of career barriers as well as their consequences is thought to be very effective in addressing the root of the problem and offering solutions. In this context, this research is based on the hypothesis that alienation is also a result of career barrier.

1.1 Career Barriers

Due to the expansion and diversification of job opportunities in industrialized societies, the increase in the world population and changing lifestyles, the required business areas increase significantly in a short time. This diversification increases the number of employees in different sectors at the same time. Being involved in any profession and continuing to work becomes systematic with the industrialization and the expansion of the service sector. Thus, individuals are faced with concepts such as changing the existing position, appointment, promotion, leaving the job in their business life. These changes and developments have created a concept that deals with the before, during and after of working life and has placed itself as a "career" in both professional life and scientific literature. Career is defined by Tortop (1994), as the progress of a person step by step and steadily in any field of work, gaining experience and skills throughout the years that he can work; by Stone (2003), as a process that includes all of the work done by the individual, the positions they are in, and the attitudes and behaviors related to these positions; by Erdoğan (2003) as a concept that includes the positions that the individuals have been in throughout their working life and the work done in these positions; and by Aytaç (2005) as the work done by employees during their working life as a continuity that includes the development and progress in business life. İnandı, Tunç, and Uslu (2013) express the common emphasis of definitions as the increase in social prestige and income level with the increase in the position in working life. In general, career is a flow that deals with the positions of the individuals during their working life, the attitudes they have developed towards their profession, and the income gained in return for the performance displayed due to these attitudes and the status of the individual.

Developments and outcomes in the career process can be both individual and organizational. Bakioglu and Inandi (2001) define the individual dimension as the ability to create a productive work environment with high job satisfaction by improving one's career; and the organizational dimension as the ability of the individual to exhibit an effective performance in terms of serving the organization with this high efficiency and motivation. Considering the reflection of these two factors on social life at the same time, which cannot be evaluated independently of each other, it is seen that the concept of career has a multifaceted effect area. This effect benefits both the individual, the organization and the social life. Occupational groups from which the organization and the society are profitable according to the career trajectory are more preferred areas in the society. Considering income, status, high motivation and productivity, job satisfaction and working conditions, academicians constitute one of the leading professions in this sense. Academicianship is seen as a profession that draws attention at this point, especially since the knowledge and experiences gained in the long term are seen more useful in the career process.

Being an academician aims to do research in universities, educate students and shed light on social problems in the light of scientific data. It can be stated that academicians have a wide field of study such as seniority, field of study, faculty and university variables, management and they go through a long-term process. However, considering the titles such as promotion and appointment, gender factor, freedom to publish scientific publications, participating in research and projects and engaging in professional development activities, academicians constitute one of the occupational groups with the most career barriers. In this profession, which has long career steps, both maintaining the existing title and encountering various difficulties during promotion periods are a common problem for academicians. The understanding that universities are independent within themselves is being broken day by day by the governments, and the structures that change with the policies of the country affect academicians in many ways and may present themselves as a problem. Foreign language knowledge encountered in the scientific research process, the number of publications, arbitrary practices in promotions and appointments, organizational conflicts and communication problems (Inandi, Tunç, & Uslu, 2013), lack of resources, not being able to spare time for research, using scientific knowledge as an indicator of power and status and Turning into a relationship of interest, conflicts with administrators and economic difficulties are the main problems faced by academicians. In the literature, these obstacles, especially in terms of recruitment, appointment, promotion, financial difficulties and scientific publication, are titled as demographic factors, disagreements, lack of resources, institutional relations and professional attitudes.

In academicians, which is an artistic profession, each individual has a unique idea and action plan. For this reason, the differences of opinion that arise in scientific research, in making joint decisions, in the communication network with managers and in relations with colleagues, make themselves felt intensely. While these differences can be used as an advantage, they can often lead to undesirable consequences. In order to advance the careers of lecturers, both their managers and colleagues can act together with YÖK and reflect this situation to the academicians as a career barrier. In addition, it is thought that this is caused by the current political structuring in the country and the staffing formed depending on it. Therefore, it is seen that differences of opinion and different political attitudes are perceived as an obstacle to the careers of academicians. Considering the lack of resources, another subtitle, the idea that a large amount of resource budget should be allocated to universities in order to ensure the development of scientific research around the world comes forward. However, in Turkey in recent years in the university budget allocated to the statement of expenditure expected to show decreased growth are examined, it is seen that the costs kept to a minimum. Looking at the distribution of 2018/2019 Higher Education Budgets Allocations, we have reduced the expenditures of goods and services by one third (33%) and capital expenditures, which express investment expenditures in higher education, by 30 percent (Eğitim-Sen, 2018), most of the resource is the essential needs of the academician. It is observed that he goes to salary payments and premium debts. Dost and Cenkseven (2007) stated that the highest rate of lecturers was "economic problems" (66%), then the insufficiency of resources (books, articles, etc.) (20.1%), and finally, the insufficiency of facilities such as internet and computers in the business environment (% 10.7) stated that they had problems. This situation shows that there is a lack of academic and technical infrastructure in universities. Institutional relations, on the other hand, include the division of labor and relations between staff in universities, which are a very crowded group in organizational terms. However, when looking at the relationships and communication network of the academic staff, it is seen that the job descriptions are not

clearly differentiated. This situation creates a problem for faculty members to maintain their institutional relations and creates a limitation in conducting their research. Mengi and Schreglmann (2013) stated that the support of academic staff and staff working in the organization for scientific research was insufficient in their research, and that the answer to the question about getting the necessary service was mostly disagree. The fact that all personnel have a research culture in terms of scientific productivity in university organizations positively affects the motivation of the academic staff and plays an encouraging role in academic studies. On the other hand, considering the relations between colleagues, the time periods spent with colleagues are also quite long, especially since universities are organizations that require working outside of busy hours. While the shared work environment and similar study areas are expected to increase motivation and academic encouragement, it is seen that there is no such effect in the literature. In Murat's (2003) study, faculty members ranked third among the problems that bother them the most, while in Sarioğlu's (2010) study, when academicians show high performance, they are respected and rewarded by the organization and their colleagues. They state that they did not encounter them and that this was not important. It is seen that peer attitudes are an important factor affecting the career lives of academicians in creating an academic culture that supports both the individual and the scientific publication.

The career barriers faced by academicians address a large part of their professional life. This share is seen as a serious obstacle in obtaining the title, which is one of the main goals of academicians, and in the advancement of scientific knowledge. These obstacles do not only prevent the progress of science and scientists, but reduce the sense of belonging, trust and justice in universities, and increase the level of destructive conflict and alienation. As a matter of fact, Özdemir, Yüksel, Cemaloğlu, Çakmak, Çeliköz, Erişen, and Doğan (2006) concluded that academicians do not find the current appointment and promotion criteria as objective and fair, and this situation increases the alienation among academicians. In this respect, determining the relationship between career barriers and other factors in terms of the predictive power of academic alienation constitutes the main purpose of the study.

1.2 Alienation

Alienation, which includes feelings of desperation and loneliness, is as old as the times when the individuals established a relationship with themselves and those around them. While Seeman (1959) defines alienation as a decrease in the capacity to act, it addresses five sub-dimensions as powerlessness, meaninglessness, irregularity, isolation and self-alienation. Explaining that the phenomenon of alienation in individuals and organizations instead of a single definition will manifest itself in the aforementioned five situations, Seeman mentions that these five dimensions complement each other. Erjem (2005) defines alienation as an inhumane situation, the loss of the essence and essence of the human being, the disintegration of the psycho-social dimensions of his existence, distancing and rupture from each other. In the definitions made, the expression "moving away from the current self or the organization" is frequently emphasized. Yapıcı (2004) expresses this as separation from others and mentions the importance of being deprived of warm relationships. When all these definitions are taken into consideration, it can be stated that alienation involves the attitude of isolating the self from the individuals, the group or the organization they are in, not establishing adequate communication and relationship with themselves or with other members of the organization.

Weakness, one of the sub-dimensions of alienation, is a feeling that occurs when the individuals have difficulty in controlling themselves and their environment. Because control brings with it the ability to cope. Inability of the individuals to exhibit this skill causes them to experience weakness. Seeman, in a similar way, explains powerlessness as the lack of control over the products produced by the individual and the tools used in this process (Yıldız & Alım, 2019). The individual, whose effectiveness on products and vehicles has decreased, feels powerless in solving problems with their environment and managers, being involved in production, and processing what is produced. The meaninglessness is the inability of the individual to perceive the act or the production process involved. This obscurity creates a gap by making it difficult for the individual to attribute meaning to things. Seeman (1959) defines meaninglessness as the individual's inability to know what to believe and what general truths to believe (Elma, 2003). Therefore, the individuals cannot make sense of their work, entering into an inaction and falling into a void. The fact that the task and job criteria given to the individual are

not consistent with the criteria that the individual should actually do, prompts him to question. This contradiction will cause the person to not be able to comprehend the function he / she is in and to create feelings of meaninglessness in him. The sub-dimension of irregularity (normlessness) describes the individual who does not adopt the principles of the order operating with social norms. Şimşek, Çelik, Akgemici, and Fettahoğlu (2006) define this situation as not being able to find the principles and measurements that will direct the behavior and to resort to socially unapproved ways to reach the goal. At this point, the individuals feel the need to create their own rules because they cannot benefit from the existing order in their behavior and attitude system. Therefore, the general rules do not make sense for his behavior. At this point, irregularity appears as a structure that complements each other with meaninglessness. Social Isolation sub-dimension is also considered as isolation, the individuals' detachment from themselves or from groups and organizations. Yılmaz and Sarpkaya (2009) state that isolation can be caused by the individuals' withdrawal from the society or by their exclusion from their social circle. In this case, isolation causes the individuals to be unable to relate and communicate with their social circle. Şimşek, Çelik, Akgemici, and Fettahoğlu (2006) state that the alienated individual feels like a 'lonely island' that is separated from his friends, has no ties to them, and experiences a kind of isolation. This isolation causes the individuals to find themselves meaningless and inaction. Therefore, the individuals begin to exhibit a weak and abstentional attitude in achieving the goals with the organization they is in. The isolation dimension of alienation overlaps with the meaningless dimension at this point. The isolation dimension of alienation overlaps with the meaningless dimension at this point. Finally, self-alienation (Self-Cooling) is associated with the weakening of the individuals' ties with their ego. Yıldız and Buyer (2019) explain this weak link as the individual's concern with external factors such as money and security, rather than the internal factors of the job, and thus emphasize the lack of satisfaction from the work done. Therefore, they have difficulties in adapting to the organization. Başaran (1998), on the other hand, evaluates self-alienation as a person's alienation from his / her own realities, and the behaviors, values, norms developed by a person are not based on their needs and desires. It can be defined as an individual's engaging in attitudes that do not represent themselves, and exhibiting these attitudes rather than behaviors in which they are a tool of intrinsic motivation.

Alienation in academicians generally arises in situations that are caused by academicians' work outside of their basic duties and structures within universities. If the employee has a large number of responsibilities and job descriptions are not restricted, the level of alienation may increase. Considering the academic title of YÖK (1981), it is seen that the job descriptions of academicians in universities are not in a restricted system. On the other hand, the fact that universities' specific systems, hierarchies, communication and relationship styles cannot be carried out in a constructive and supportive manner makes systematic work difficult and causes an increase in the level of alienation of academicians. Alienation, which affects both individuals themselves and the system they live in (Kesik & Cömert, 2014), also affects the quality of the individual and the organization, and Başaran (2000) regards this as a situation that harms the organization. Because the profession of academicians requires a free understanding and working in a democratic environment.

1.3 Aim of the Study

The aim of this study is to reveal the relationship between career barriers faced by academicians and their level of alienation. Both career barriers and alienation are problems that employees frequently encounter today. These problems are quite common in the academic community as well. Determining the relationship of these two variables with each other is important in terms of guiding the solution of the problems.

For this purpose, answers to the following questions are sought:

1. Do the career barriers faced by academicians differ significantly by gender?
2. Do academicians' alienation levels differ significantly by gender?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the career barriers faced by academicians and their level of alienation?
4. Do career barriers experienced by academicians predict alienation?

2. Method

2.1 Research Model

This research was conducted using the correlational survey model, one of the quantitative research methods, in order to reveal the relationship between the career barriers experienced by academicians and their alienation. In the correlational survey model, it is aimed to reveal the relationships between two or more variables and their degrees (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009; Karasar, 2012). In survey studies, the idea is that if people want to know what people think, it should be asked directly (Christensen, Johnson, & Turner, 2015). In this regard, the research data were collected through face-to-face interviews with the academicians participating in the study.

2.2 Study group

Research data were collected from academicians at a state university located in Turkey in 2019-2020 academic year. All academicians who were available within the scope of the study and who agreed to participate in the study were included in the study. 93 (46%) of the academicians participating in the study are female and 109 (54%) of them are male.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

Research data were collected using the Career Barriers Scale (CBS) and the Alienation from Academicians Scale (AAS).

2.3.1 Career Barriers Scale

It was developed by Inandı, Tunç, and Uslu (2013) to measure the career barriers faced by academicians. The scale consists of 5 factors and 19 items. Factors are, respectively, Demographic Variables, Differences of Opinion, Insufficient Resources, Institutional Relations and Colleague Attitudes. Internal consistency coefficients obtained while developing the scale were calculated as Demographic Variables, 55; Differences of Opinion, 83; Insufficient Resources, 75; Institutional Relations, 90 and Colleague Attitudes, 95. The internal consistency coefficient for the overall scale was found to be 88. Within the scope of this research, the internal consistency coefficient for the overall scale was calculated as 88.

2.3.2 Academician Alienation Scale

It was developed by Yıldız and Alıcı (2019) in order to reveal the alienation of academicians towards their profession. The scale of alienation from academicians consists of 5 factors and 21 items. Factors are named as Self Alienation, Alienation from Scientific Research, Alienation from Teaching, Isolation and Powerlessness. Internal consistency coefficients for the sub-factors of the scale are Self Alienation, 79; Alienation from Scientific Research, 79; Alienation to Education, 76; While Insulation was determined as 68 and Powerlessness as 67, the internal consistency coefficient for the overall scale was calculated as 0.867. Within the scope of this research, the internal consistency coefficient for the overall scale was found to be 81.

3. Results

In the results section of the study, there are findings regarding whether there is a significant difference between Career Barriers and Alienation levels experienced by academicians according to gender variables, whether there is a relationship between career barriers and alienation, and career barriers predict alienation.

Table 1: T-Test Results of Academicians' Opinions Regarding Career Barrier Levels According to Gender Variable

Carrier Barriers	Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	Sd	t	df	p
Demographic Variables	Female	93	3,6071	0,72	2,505	200	0,013*
	Male	109	3,3349	0,80			
Differences of Opinion	Female	93	3,5735	1,043	0,968	200	0,334
	Male	109	3,4312	1,040			
Insufficient Resources	Female	93	3,9072	0,72	2,263	200	0,025*
	Male	109	3,6525	0,85			
Institutional Relations	Female	93	3,8065	1,13	2,310	200	0,022*
	Male	109	3,4464	1,07			
Colleague Attitudes	Female	93	3,3638	1,14	1,197	200	0,233
	Male	109	3,1858	0,96			

*p<0.05

When Table 1 was examined, it was seen that female academicians experienced more obstacles than male academicians in terms of demographic variables ($p = 0.013$), insufficient resources ($p = 0.025$), and institutional relations ($p = 0.022$), which are sub-dimensions of career barriers. This difference is statistically significant. On the other hand, there was no significant difference in opinion differences ($p = 0.334$) and colleague attitudes ($p = 0.233$) dimensions.

Table 2: T-Test Results of Academicians' Opinions Regarding Academic Alienation Levels According to Gender Variable

Academic Alienation	Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	Sd	t	df	p
Self Alienation	Female	93	2,1006	0,56	-1,731	200	0,085
	Male	109	2,2298	0,50			
Alienation from Scientific Research	Female	93	2,6364	0,82	1,372	200	0,172
	Male	109	2,4655	0,92			
Alienation from Teaching	Female	93	2,6517	0,83	0,772	200	0,441
	Male	109	2,5646	0,76			
Isolation	Female	93	3,7312	0,84	1,704	200	0,090
	Male	109	3,5321	0,81			
Powerlessness	Female	93	2,8676	0,916	2,586	200	0,010*
	Male	109	2,5323	0,919			

*p<0.05

According to the results of the t test regarding whether the gender variable in Table 2 made a significant difference according to the sub-dimensions of Alienation, we were self-alienation ($p = 0.085$), alienation from scientific research ($p = 0.172$), alienation from teaching ($p = 0.441$) and isolation ($p = 0.090$), there was no significant difference in the dimensions. There is a meaningful difference in favor of female academicians in the dimension of powerlessness ($p = 0.010$). Female academicians feel more powerless than male academicians.

Table 3: Results of Correlation Analysis Regarding the Relationship Between Academicians' Career Barriers and Academic Alienation Levels

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	$\bar{X}$	Sd
Demographic Reliabies	1										3,46	,77
Differences of Opinion	,247	1									3,49	1,04
Insufficient Resources	,290	,410	1								3,76	,80
Institutional Relations	,267	,480	,383	1							3,61	1,11
Colleague Attitudes	,221	,657	,386	,544	1						3,26	1,05
Self Alienation	-,131	,131	,128	,187**	,107	1					2,17	,53
Alienation from Academic Research	,101	-,049	-,126	,005	,061	,023	1				2,54	,88
Alienation from Teaching	,163*	-,093	-,126	-,010	-,002	-,073	,510	1			2,60	,79
Isolation	,308**	,790**	,598**	,545**	,793**	,067	-,038	-,079	1		3,62	,83
Powerlessness	,093	-,130	-,009	-,023	-,041	-,122	,702	,518	-,118	1	2,68	,93

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

When the relationship between career barriers experienced by academicians and their alienation is examined, a positive relationship has been found between the dimension of isolation and all dimensions of career barriers. A positive and strong relationship was found between the isolation dimension and Colleague Attitudes ($r = ,793$) and Opinion Differences ($r = ,790$). A positive and moderate relationship was also found between Isolation and Demographic Variables ($r = ,3089$; Lack of Resources ($r = ,598$) and Institutional Relationships ($r = ,545$).

It has also been revealed that there is a positive and weak relationship between Self-Alienation and Institutional Relationships and between Demographic Variables and Education Alienation.

Table 4. Results of Multiple Regression Analysis Regarding the Level of Career Barriers of Academicians Predicting Academic Alienation

Alienation	Self Alienation				Alienation from Academic Research				Alienation from Teaching				Isolation				Powerlessness			
	B	SH	B	T	B	SH	B	T	B	SH	B	T	B	SH	B	T	B	SH	B	T
Demographic Variables	-,151	,050	-,222	-3,048	,166	,084	,146	1,975	,230	,075	,224	3,061	,041	,035	,039	1,188	,151	,089	,126	1,690
Differences of Opinion	,039	,048	,077	,815	-,112	,081	-,132	-1,374	-,119	,073	-,156	-,1,641	,312	,034	,390	9,248	-,187	,087	-,209	-2,161
Insufficient Resources	,067	,052	,102	1,295	-,204	,088	-,186	-2,326	-,173	,078	-,175	-,2,208	,265	,036	,257	7,307	,017	,093	,015	,183
Institutional Relations	,091	,041	,191	2,247	-,002	,069	-,002	-,023	-,008	,061	,011	,125	,017	,028	,023	,592	,004	,073	,005	,059
Colleague Attitudes	-,019	,049	-,038	-,390	,158	,083	,189	1,912	,085	,074	,113	1,155	,329	,034	,417	9,598	,053	,088	,060	,601
	R=,290 R ² =0,084 F=3,393 p<,05 (,004)				R=,237 R ² =,056 F=2,327 p<,05 (,044)				R=,270 R ² =,073 F=3,076 p<,05 (,011)				R=,904 R ² =,817 F=174,995 p<,05 (,000)				R=,191 R ² =,036 F=1,478 p>,05 (,199)			

According to the results of multiple regression analysis conducted to test whether the career barriers experienced by academicians predict alienation, all dimensions of career barriers explain the isolation experienced by academicians to a great extent ($R^2 = ,817$). It is possible that the isolation of academicians can be explained by career barriers to a great extent

4. Discussion

One of the first professions that come to mind when the concept of career is mentioned is being an academic. For this reason, it maintains its place in the agenda as one of the most discussed topics by career lecturers in higher education. Especially worries about promotion and stress situations are among the most important problems of

academicians. Therefore, in this study, the relationship between career barriers faced by academicians and their level of alienation has been tried to be determined.

First of all, it was examined whether there is a significant difference between the views of academicians about career barriers they have experienced according to their gender. According to these results, female academicians stated that they experienced more obstacles than male academicians in terms of demographic variables, lack of resources and institutional relations, which are the sub-dimensions of career barriers. In demographic variables including foreign language, course load, economic and family obligations, the reason why women experience more obstacles is that in the traditional family structure, women are expected to stay at home instead of participating in business life, to carry out tasks such as home service work and child care. Women who overcome these responsibilities and enter the business life both try to fulfill these responsibilities and have to undertake the foreign language and heavy lessons that require extra effort. In professional life, the fact that senior managers are generally male and social relations are more than women can make men more advantageous in accessing resources. In societies where democracy is not well established, problems are also encountered in inter-institutional relations. Especially when it is desired to be advertised in universities, sometimes within the university itself, sometimes at YÖK, sometimes by the government, the government's suspension of the advertisements and the lack of good inter-institutional relations may have led women academicians to think this way. The results of the research conducted by Er (2008) overlap with the results of this study in terms of demographic variables and lack of resources. In the study conducted by Bakioğlu and Yaman (2004), similar results were obtained from the demographic variables of this study, especially on foreign languages. Belkıs (2016) also reached similar results with the results of my study. Especially 11 out of 14 female academicians among the participants stated that they mostly faced with time problems after they became mothers. On the other hand, it can be said that female academicians are more deprived of the gender stereotypes imposed on women by the society on issues such as going to foreign countries, participating in monthly or annual international seminars, applying to exchange programs. The excessive course burden creates a situation against female academicians, and the fact that they have multiple roles in the balance of home-work-child responsibilities may have caused women to respond in this direction.

Considering the level of alienation experienced by academicians by gender, female academicians stated that they experienced more powerlessness than men in the dimension of alienation. Weakness is a feeling that occurs when the individual has difficulty controlling themselves and their environment. Because control brings with it the ability to cope. Inability of the individual to exhibit this skill causes them to experience weakness. In the literature, it is seen that academicians frequently experience weakness in universities (Halaçoğlu, 2008; Güneri, 2010; Minaslı, 2013). In this study, female academicians stated that they experienced more powerlessness than men due to various problems they experienced. In the dimension of powerlessness, which is directly related to the exhibited performance and feeling self-sufficient, the fact that women experience a higher level of weakness compared to men may be due to the inability to feel academically competent in the classroom or in relations with students, and the transfer of the energies and interests of female academicians to home-business life. Şentürk, Ünnü, and Kesken (2017), in their research on academicians, concluded that the unfair distribution in the division of labor in the home and the time they devoted to jobs that could be described as "second shift" by female academicians decreased their academic performance. The female academic, who mostly undertakes the responsibility of home and children with a traditional understanding, has to share her current performance as a home-child responsibility and a student-teaching responsibility. As a matter of fact, in the metaphorical study of Ehtiyar, Solmaz and Can (2019) called *Being a Woman Academician*, the metaphor of "having multitasking" is the most recurring theme. In the study conducted by Başarır and Sarı (2015) to determine the perceptions of being a female academician metaphorically, female academicians' emphasis on the theme of 'being a woman academician as a person with multitasking and responsibilities' shows similar findings. Having multiple duties and being obliged to carry out these duties may have caused female academicians to experience higher levels of powerlessness compared to male academicians. Of course, many reasons may have affected the powerlessness of academicians, especially women academicians. Macarie and Moldovan (2012) base one of these on the theory of attribution, when women perform above expectations, this success is associated with luck, and when they fail to achieve the expected success, this situation is based on personal characteristics such as failure and not acting professionally; On the contrary, superior success for male managers; with wit and skill; low performance is

explained by external factors such as bad luck. According to this theory, the association of low performance of female academicians with lack of skills and low achievement suggests that the fact that male academicians are not confronted with such a deficiency creates a vicious circle in the level of powerlessness of female academicians. One might think that the association of women's every failure with their educational deficiency also creates a learned helplessness of powerlessness. There are studies that do not overlap with the results of this study (Güneri, 2010; Akbulut, 2017).

Considering the relationship between academicians' career barriers and academic alienation levels, all of the career barriers faced by academicians have a significant relationship with isolation, which is one of the sub-dimensions of alienation. As the career barrier of academicians increases, their level of isolation increases. As the career barriers arising from the demographic variable increase, the alienation of academicians from teaching and their barriers stemming from institutional relations increase, their level of self-alienation increases. As the career barriers arising from the demographic variable increase, the alienation of academicians from teaching and their barriers stemming from institutional relations increase, their level of self-alienation increases. Regardless of men or women, academicians can be prevented for various reasons at universities. These obstacles may sometimes be related to the attitudes of colleagues, sometimes the attitudes and behaviors of managers, sometimes for political and institutional reasons, sometimes for economic reasons and sometimes for personal reasons. Of course, personal reasons can make the individual less unhappy, while other reasons can make people quite unhappy and even manifest themselves until the emergence of serious symptoms. These obstacles faced by academicians can sometimes lead to their alienation. In the context of this study, academicians experience alienation, especially in terms of isolation. Isolation means getting away from the individual's cat, environment and groups. This isolation can sometimes pull the academician away from the society and sometimes the society can exclude himself (Yılmaz & Sarpkaya, 2009). Şimşek, Çelik, Akgemici, and Fettahoğlu (2006) express isolation as an individual's experience of isolation. This isolation may cause the individual to find themselves meaningless and inaction. There are academicians who have not been able to recruit their staff for years due to the above-mentioned political, economic, institutional relations, managerial attitudes and behaviors. Even aside from being unable to recruit their staff, they are exposed to intimidation, marginalization and intimidation, and the person withdraws himself from everything, alienates himself from teaching and himself, and reaches the level of isolation. Arı (2007), Mengi, and Schreglmann (2012) stated in their study that one of the most important problems was economics. Güneri (2010), in his study on academicians' alienation from work, found that the item with the highest average in the isolation sub-dimension was "I prefer to stay away from people I do not agree with" and the lowest "I find my social environment very boring." This clearly shows that academicians are not socially inadequate and ineffective, but that they diverge politically and ideologically. Therefore, it leads to the conclusion that every academic comes together with those who are like him and that the academic community behaves more conservatively rather than the richness of differences. Inandı, Tunç and Uslu (2012), in their study with academicians, revealed that their career barriers had a negative impact on their management processes, unsuitability of working conditions, economic reasons, and the consequences that led to a decrease in academicians' job satisfaction. The decrease in job satisfaction can also cause them to become alienated and alienated from the job.

Considering the predictive levels of academicians' career barriers to their alienation, the most striking point occurred in the dimension of isolation. Career barriers predict isolation by approximately 82%. It predicts other dimensions at a low level. As a result, career barriers experienced in this study cause the most isolation among academicians. One of the most important problems of higher education is the difficulties faced by academicians in their career process. Experiencing these difficulties are emphasized in various studies (Elliott, 1990; Marginson, 2000; Taylor, 2001; Tekeli, 2002-2003; Aktay, 2003; Martin, 2004;), which reflects negatively both on the academicians themselves, on the institutional functioning and on the teaching dimension. In Karakütük, Tunç, Bülbül, and Özdem (2008) research, it is noteworthy that the basic problems of all teaching staff related to their professions are related to the academic promotion process. It would not be reasonable to expect an academic who is exposed to mobbing in the working environment, who is not peaceful, has low job satisfaction and motivation, and has high alienation and burnout, to be truly beneficial to science, education and society (Inandı, 2009).

For this reason, female academicians who experienced more obstacles than men regarding demographic variables, institutional relations and lack of resources also stated that they experienced more alienation than men in isolation, which is the sub-dimension of alienation.

This research has been done on the career barriers and alienation of academicians, researchers can investigate the relationships between academicians' career barriers and burnout, career barriers, and organizational ties. The obstacles that may be faced by academicians in higher education should be removed, taking into account the scale of their merit, and appropriate working conditions should be provided for them. Regardless of the academic's political view, ethnicity and gender, career planning should be ensured, taking into account his contribution to sharpening.

References

- Akbulut, S. (2017). *Yabancılaşma olgusunun örgütsel güven ve örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışlarına etkisi üzerine bir araştırma: Adıyaman Üniversitesi örneği*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Adıyaman Üniversitesi, Adıyaman.
- Akgeyik, T. (2013). *Ulusal ve uluslararası karşılaştırmalarla öğretim üyeliği maaşı*. (1.Baskı). Ankara: SETA Yayınları.
- Aktay, Y. (2003). Üniversiteden multiversiteye taşra-merkez diyalektiği. *Toplum ve Bilim*, 97, 93-122.
- Alaçam, B. (2014). *Akademisyen hemşirelerin kariyer engelleri*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Atatürk Üniversitesi, Erzurum.
- Anaş, K. (2016). *Vakıf üniversitesi çalışanlarında örgütsel sinizm tutumunun işe yabancılaşma üzerine etkisi*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Sabahattin Zaim Üniversitesi, İstanbul.
- Arı, A. (2007). Üniversite öğretim elemanlarının sorunları. *Manas Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 9(17), 65-74.
- Arsu, Ş. U., Sunman, G., Oruç, Ş. & Tekindal, M. (2020). Türkiye'de gelişmekte olan üniversitede araştırma görevlisi olma deneyimi: Nitel bir araştırma. *Ufku Ötesi Bilim Dergisi*, (1), 109-152.
- Aryee, S., Chen, Z. X., & Budhwar, P. S. (2004). Exchange fairness and employee performance: An examination of the relationship between organizational politics and procedural justice. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 94(1), 1-14.
- Aslan, G. (2010). Öğretim üyelerinin girişimci üniversite ve üniversite sanayi işbirliği kavramlarına ilişkin görüşleri. *Eğitim Bilim Toplum Dergisi*, 8 (30), 7-22.
- Aydemir, C. (2017). *İş-Aile çatışmasının psikolojik performans üzerine etkisi: İşe yabancılaşma ve pozitif psikolojik sermayenin aracı rolü*. (Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi). Erciyes Üniversitesi, Kayseri.
- Aydın, O. T. (2017). Research performance of higher education institutions: A review on the measurements and affecting factors of research performance. *Journal of Higher Education and Science*, 7(2), 312-320.
- Aydoğan, İ. (2009). Favoritism in the Turkish Educational System: Nepotism, cronyism and patronage. *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*, 4(1).
- Aypay, A. (2001). *The relationship between organizational structures and faculty roles at colleges and universities*. Unpublished PhD dissertation. Vanderbilt University: Nashville, TN, USA
- Aypay, A. (2006). Üniversitelerde akademik etkinlik ve örgütsel davranış arasındaki ilişki. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi Dergisi*, 12(2), 175-198.
- Aytaç, M., Aytaç, S., Fırat, Z., Bayram, N. & Keser, A. (2001). *Akademisyenlerin çalışma yaşamı ve kariyer sorunları*. Bursa: Uludağ Üniversitesi Araştırma Fonu İşletmesi.
- Aytaç, S. (2005). *Çalışma yaşamında kariyer yönetimi planlaması gelişimi ve sorunları*. Bursa: Ezgi Kitabevi.
- Bakioğlu, A. & Genç, E. (2001). Araştırma görevlilerinin başarı değerlendirmeye bakışları. *Burdur Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 2.
- Bakioğlu, A. & İnandı, Y. (2001). Öğretmenin kariyer gelişiminde müdürün görevleri. *Eğitim Yönetimi Dergisi*, 28(7), 513-529.
- Bakioğlu, A. & Pekince, D. (2011). Araştırma görevlilerinin kariyer gelişimlerine bölümlerindeki destek kültürünün etkisi. Uluslararası Yükseköğretim Kongresi: Yeni Yönelişler ve Sorunlar (UYK-2011), 27-29 Mayıs 2011, İstanbul, 2(XI), (s. 1272-1280).
- Bakioğlu, A. & Yaman, E. (2004). Araştırma görevlilerinin kariyer gelişimleri: Engeller ve çözümler. *Marmara Üniversitesi Atatürk Eğitim Fakültesi Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 20, 1-20
- Başaran, İ. E. (1998). Yönetimde insan ilişkileri: Yönetimsel davranış. Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım
- Başaran, İ. E. (2000). *Örgütsel davranış*. Ankara: Feryal Matbaası.
- Başarır, F. & Sarı, M. (2015). Kadın akademisyenlerin "Kadın Akademisyen Olma" ya ilişkin algılarının metaforlar yoluyla incelenmesi. *Yükseköğretim ve Bilim Dergisi*, 5(1), 41-51.

- Belkıs, Ö. (2016). Anneliğin akademik kariyer gelişimine etkileri üzerine nitel bir araştırma. *Eğitim ve Öğretim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 5(4), 250-263.
- Bingöl, H. (2017). *Yükseköğretim kurumlarında spor eğitimi veren kadın akademisyenlerin kariyer engellerinin incelenmesi*. (Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi). İnönü Üniversitesi, Malatya.
- Bülbül, T. (2006). *Üniversite öğretim elemanı ücretlerinin akademik yaşama yansımalarının değerlendirilmesi*. (Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi). Ankara Üniversitesi, Ankara.
- Carroll, V. S. (2003). The teacher, the scholar, the self: Fitting thinking and writing into a four-four load. *College Teaching*, 51(1), 22-26.
- Christensen, L. B., Johnson, R. B. & Turner, L. A. (2015). Araştırma Yöntemleri Desen ve Analiz. (A. Aypay, Çeviri Editörü). Anı Yayıncılık, Ankara.
- Coşkun, M. K. (2008). Üniversite eğitimi ve akademisyenler: Quovadis? *Toplum ve Demokrasi Dergisi*, 2(3), 197-202
- Çetin, M. & Atan, E. (2012). İlköğretim okullarında görev yapan kadın okul yöneticilerinin “cam tavan” a ilişkin algılarının incelenmesi. *Marmara Üniversitesi Atatürk Eğitim Fakültesi Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 35, 123-136.
- Demir, H. & Okan T. (2008). Karadeniz Teknik Üniversitesi akademisyenlerinin kariyer aşamaları ve değişmeyen ihtiyaçları. *İstanbul Üniversitesi İşletme İktisadi Enstitüsü Yönetimi Dergisi*, 59, 27-42.
- Dost, M. T. ve Cenkeşen, F. (2007). Devlet ve vakıf üniversitelerinde çalışan öğretim elemanlarının mesleki sorunları. *Çukurova Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 2(16), 203-218.
- Durusoy, M. (2018). *Öğretim elemanlarının kariyerde durgunluk kaynaklarına ilişkin görüşleri*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Akdeniz Üniversitesi, Antalya.
- Eğitim Sen, (2018). 06.09.2019 tarihinde <http://egitimsen.org.tr/2019-yili-yuksekogretim-butcesi-analizi/> adlı adresten alınmıştır.
- Ehtiyar, R., Solmaz, C. ve Can, Ç. (2019). “Kadın Akademisyen” olmak: Turizm alanındaki kadın akademisyenlere yönelik bir metafor çalışması. *Seyahat ve Otel İşletmeciliği Dergisi*, 16(2), 2019, 296-318.
- Elliott, J. (1990). Educational research in crisis: Performance. *British Educational Research Journal*, 16 (1), 3-18.
- Elma, C., (2003). *İlköğretim okulu öğretmenlerinin işe yabancılaşması (Ankara ili örneği)*. (Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi). Ankara Üniversitesi, Ankara.
- Er, D. (2008). Modern Türkiye’de kadın öğretim üyelerinin konumuna ve sorunlarına sosyolojik bir yaklaşım. (Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi). Fırat Üniversitesi, Elazığ.
- Erdem, M.(2014). İş yaşamı kalitesinin işe yabancılaşmayı yordama düzeyi. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Bilimleri*, 14(2),1-26.
- Erdoğan, N. (2003). *Kariyer geliştirme*. (1. Baskı). Ankara: Nobel Yayını.
- Ergöl, Ş., Koç, G., Eroğlu, K. ve Taşkın, L. (2012). Türkiye’de kadın araştırma görevlilerinin ev ve iş yaşamlarında karşılaştıkları güçlükler. *Yükseköğretim Dergisi*, 2(1), 43-49.
- Ergün, E. (2007). *İnsan kaynakları yönetiminde kariyer planlama ve bir uygulama*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Marmara Üniversitesi, İstanbul.
- Erimez, C., & Gizir, S. (2013). Eğitim fakültesi öğrencilerinin öğretmenlik mesleğine yönelik tutumlarında fakültelerine yabancılaşmalarının rolü. *Mersin Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 9(3), 13-26.
- Erjem, Y. (2005). Eğitimde yabancılaşma olgusu ve öğretmen: Lise öğretmenleri üzerine sosyolojik bir araştırma. *Gazi Üniversitesi Türk Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 3(4), 1-22.
- Fırat, Y. B. (2012). *Öğretim elemanlarının mesleki yabancılaşma algılarının örgütsel bağlılık ve iş motivasyonu faktörleri ile modellenmesi*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Ege Üniversitesi, İzmir.
- Fraenkel, Jack R., & Wallen, Norman E. (2009). How to design and evaluate research in education (Seventh ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Gupta, N.,Kemelgor, C., Fuchs, S.veEtzkowitz, H. (2005). Triple burden on women in science: A cross-Cultural Analysis. *Current Science*, 89(8), 1382-1386.
- Gündüz, Y. (2010). Öğretmen algılarına göre kadın öğretmenlerin kariyer engellerinin incelenmesi. *Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi Dergisi*, 1(10), 133-149.
- Güneri, M. B., (2010). *Öğretim elemanlarının maruz kaldıkları yıldırma davranışlarının işe yabancılaşmaları üzerine etkisi*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Akdeniz Üniversitesi, Antalya.
- Halaçoğlu, B. (2008). *Üniversitelerde akademik personelin mesleki yabancılaşma düzeylerinin çok boyutlu incelenmesi*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Yeditepe Üniversitesi, İstanbul.
- Ismail, M. ve Rasdi, R. M. (2007). Impact of networking on career development: Experience of high-flying women academics in Malaysia. *Human Resource Development International*, 10(2), 153-168.
- İnandı, Y. ve Tunç, B. (2012). Kadın öğretmenlerin kariyer engelleri ile iş doyum düzeyleri arasındaki ilişki. *Eğitim Bilimleri Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 2(2), 203-222.
- İnandı, Y., Tunç, B. ve Uslu, F. (2013). Eğitim fakültesi öğretim elemanlarının kariyer engelleri ile iş doyumları arasındaki ilişki. *Eğitim Bilimleri Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 3(1), 219-238.

- Karaköse, T. (2014). The effects of nepotism, cronyism and political favoritism on the doctors working in public hospitals. *Ethno Med*, 8(3), 245-250.
- Karakütük, K. Tunç, B. Özdem, G. ve Bülbül, T. (2008). *Eğitim fakültelerinin öğretim elemanı profili*. Ankara: Ankara Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Yayınları.
- Karataş, T., Özen, Ş. ve Gülnar, E. (2017). Akademisyenlerin kariyer basamakları ve kariyer yaşamı. *Sosyal ve Beşeri Bilimler Dergisi*, 1(4),
- Kaya, Z. D. Ve Küçükşen, K. (2016). Yönetici pozisyonundaki akademisyen kadınlarda aile-iş özel yaşam dengesi. *The Journal of Academic Social Sciences*, 37(37), 662-662.
- Kesen, M. (2016). Öğretim elemanlarının işe yabancılaşmasının etik liderlik ve demografik değişkenler açısından incelenmesi: Uygulamalı bir çalışma. *Akademik Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 22(4), 118-134.
- Kesik, F. ve Cömert, M. (2014). İlköğretim okullarında görev yapan öğretmenlerin işe yabancılaşma düzeylerine ilişkin algıları. *İnönü Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 1(15), 27-46.
- Korkut, H., Muştan, T., ve Yalçınkaya, M. (1999). Araştırma görevlilerinin sorunları. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi Dergisi*, 17, 19-36.
- Macarie, F. C. Ve Moldovan, O. (2012). Gender Discrimination in Management Theoretical and Empirical Perspectives. *Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences*, 35, 153-172.
- Marginson, S. (2000). Rethinking academic work in the global era. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 22 (1), 23-35.
- Martin, J. J. (2004). Simplifying the academic hierarchy. *Academe*, 88 (6), 36
- McCall, L., Liddell, M., O'Neil, J. O. ve Coman G. (2000). Strategies to increase the representation of women on the academic staff of the faculty of medicine at Monash University. *Higher Education*, 39, 131-149.
- Mengi, F. ve Schreglmann, S. (2013). Akademisyenlik bağlamında bilimsel üretkenliği etkileyen çevresel faktörler. *Amasya Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi* 2(1), 1-17.
- Minaslı, A. V. (2013). *Örgüt kültürü ve örgütsel yabancılaşma arasındaki ilişki: Konuyla ilgili bir araştırma*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Trakya Üniversitesi, Edirne.
- Murat, M. (2003). Üniversite öğretim elemanlarında tükenmişlik. *Türk Psikolojik Danışma ve Rehberlik Dergisi*, 2,(19), 25-34.
- Odabaşı, F. H., Fırat, M., İzmirli, S., Çankaya, S. ve Mısırlı, Z. A. (2010). Küreselleşen dünyada akademisyen olmak. *Anadolu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 3(10), 127-142.
- Odabaşı, F., Fırat, M., İzmirli, S., Çankaya, S. ve Mısırlı, A. (2010). Küreselleşen dünyada akademisyen olmak. *Anadolu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 10(3), 127-142.
- Onay, M. ve Vezneli, Z. (2012). Sınırsız ve çok yönlü kariyer: Akademisyenlerin yükseltme ölçütlerine ilişkin görüşleri. *Yükseköğretim Dergisi*, 7(2), 82-93.
- Osmanoğlu, Ö. (2016). Hegel'den Marcuse'ye yabancılaşma olgusu. *Üsküdar Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 3, 65-92.
- Özdemir, M. Ç., Yüksel, G., Cemaloğlu, N., Çakmak, M., Çeliköz, N., Erişen, Y. ve Doğan, O. (2006). *Türkiye'de Öğretim Elemanları: Türkiye Üniversiteleri Öğretim Elemanları Araştırması*. Ankara: Gazi Üniversitesi.
- Öztekin, E., Özer, F., Belin, M., Büyüksolak, A., Ertaş, G., Gülbak, g. M., Pesen, M., Şeker, V. ve Türkmen, C. (2020). Öğretim üyeleri ve araştırma görevlileri perspektifinden fakültenin araştırma potansiyeli: Boğaziçi Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi durumu. *Boğaziçi Üniversitesi Eğitim Dergisi*, 37(2), 107-122.
- Rosenblum, S., Firestone, W. A. (1987). *Alienation and commitment of high school students and teachers*. 25 Ocak 2021'de http://eric.ed.gov/ERICWebPortal/custom/ortlets/recordDetails/detailmini.jsp?_nfpb=true&_ERICExtSearch_SearchValue_0=ED289930&ERICExtSearch_SearchType_0=no&accno=ED289930 adlı adresten alınmıştır.
- Sarı, E. G. (2018). *Akademisyenlerin mobbing algılarının örgütsel yabancılaşma düzeyleri ile ilişkisi (Munzur Üniversitesi Örneği)*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesi, Burdur.
- Sarıoğlu, S. (2010). *Akademisyenlerin motivasyonlarını etkileyen faktörlerin belirlenmesi: Bir araştırma*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek lisans Tezi). İnönü Üniversitesi, Malatya.
- Seeman, M. (1959). *On the meaning of alienation*. *American Sociological Review*, 24(6), 783-791.
- Stone, L. (2003). Work family conflict coping strategies adopted by female married professionals in Hong Kong. *Women in Management*, 18, 23-26.
- Süngü, H. (2013). Akademisyen ücretlerine ilişkin karşılaştırmalı bir analiz. *Turkish Studies*, 8(8), 1187-1205.
- Şentürk, B., Ünnü, N. A. A., ve Kesken, J. (2017). İş yaşamında toplumsal cinsiyetin etkisi: Türkiye üniversiteleri örneği. *Uluslararası İktisadi ve İdari İncelemeler Dergisi*, 16. *UİK Özel Sayısı*, 879-892.
- Şimşek, M., Çelik, A., Akgemci, T., & Fettahoğlu, T. (2006). Örgütlerde yabancılaşmanın yönetimi araştırması. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 15, 569-587.

- Taylor, J. (2001). The impact of performance indicators on the work of university academics: Evidence from Australian Universities. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 55(1), 42-61.
- Tekeli, İ. (2002-2003). Sosyal bilimcilerin performanslarının değerlendirilmesinde kullanılan ölçütleri tartışmaya açmak. *Toplum ve Bilim*, 95, 159-170.
- Tortop, N. (1994). *Personel yönetimi*. Ankara: Yargı Yayınları.
- Tunç, B. (2007). *Akademik unvan olgusu akademik yükseltme ve atama sürecinin değerlendirilmesi*, (Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi). Ankara Üniversitesi, Ankara.
- Tülübaş, T. (2017). *Orta kariyer evresinde bulunan akademisyenlerin mesleki kimlik alguları: Kolektif araçsal durum çalışması*. (Yayımlanmamış doktora Tezi). Kocaeli Üniversitesi, Kocaeli.
- Tülübaş, T. ve Celep, C. (2014). Öğretim elemanlarının sessiz kalma nedenleri. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 29(1), 280-297.
- Wagner, J. A. (1995). Studies of individualism-collectivism: effects of cooperation in groups. *Academy of Management Journal*, 38(1), 152-172.
- Yapıcı, M. (2004). Eğitim ve yabancılaşma. *Uluslararası İnsan Bilimleri Dergisi*, 1(1), 1-9.
- Yıldız, S. Ve Alici, D. (2019). Akademisyenliğe yabancılaşma ölçeğinin geliştirilmesi: Geçerlik ve güvenilirlik çalışması. *Yükseköğretim Dergisi*, 9(1), 49-58.
- Yılmaz, E., ve Özdemir, G. (2012). Türkiye’de kadın akademisyen ve araştırmacıların karşılaştıkları sorunlar ve tarıma bakış açıları. *Tekirdağ Ziraat Fakültesi Dergisi*, 9(2).
- Yılmaz, K. Ve Şahin, T. (2016). Eğitim fakültelerindeki araştırma görevlilerinin mesleki deneyimlerinin incelenmesi: araştırma görevlisi olmanın anlamına ilişkin fenomenolojik bir çalışma. *Marmara Üniversitesi Atatürk Eğitim Fakültesi Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 44, 143-168
- Yılmaz, S. ve Sarpkaya, P. (2009). Eğitim örgütlerinde yabancılaşma ve yönetimi. *Uluslararası İnsan Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2(6),
- YÖK, (1981). 04.09.2019 tarihinde <https://www.yok.gov.tr/Sayfalar/PageNotFound.aspx?requestUrl=https://www.yok.gov.tr/documents/37915040/38672190/2547+say%C4%B1%C4%B1%20Y%C3%BCksek%C3%B6%C4%9Fretim+Kanunu.pdf/954efd63-dec8-4584-8bc9-b3a58968f2da> adlı adresten alınmıştır.